

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THALASSEMIA PATIENTS IN KHAIRPUR, SINDH: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20022022>

Keywords

Thalassaemia, Prevalence, Blood groups, Hb level

Article History

Received: 27December 2025

Accepted: 08February 2026

Published: 25February 2026

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Abstract

Introduction: Thalassaemia is an inherited blood disorder caused by mutation that causes reduced or non production of functional haemoglobin, leading to anemia. Thalassaemia is a significant global health issue, with a high burden of cases in Pakistan. It requires regular blood transfusion, iron chelating therapy or a stem cell transplant.

Objective: The current study was designed to analyze the epidemiological characteristics of thalassaemia patients in Khairpur, Sindh by filling questionnaire.

Materials and Methods: The data of 97 patients was collected by interviewing patients and their parents from Fatimid Foundation Thalassaemia Center at District Khairpur Mir's, Sindh.

Results: The calculated results were 73.2% patients with age group of 0-9 years, 22.7% patients from age group of 10-17 years and 4.1% patients from age group 18-25years. The prevalence of Male patients was greater that were 52 patients than female patients that were 45. The patients with B blood group have more prevalence (35.1%) while AB blood group patients have low prevalence (8.2%).

Conclusion: The Current study highlights a higher burden of thalassaemia among younger age groups, with notable variations across gender and blood groups. These findings emphasize the need for early screening, improved management, and preventive strategies in high-risk populations.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to studies Thalassaemia is found common genetic disorder of the blood and found in various population groups in the world¹. Thalassaemia is an inherited blood disorder caused by mutation that causes reduced or non production of functional haemoglobin, leading to anemia. Thalassaemia is a significant global health issue, with a high burden of cases in Pakistan². Thalassaemia disorder is caused by less

hemoglobin (Hb) production due to mutations in either alpha globin chains or beta globin chains³. It requires regular blood transfusion, iron chelating therapy or a stem cell transplant⁴. The symptoms of thalassaemia depend upon severity i.e minor, intermedia and major and often appear in children aged even few months. The symptoms may include anemia, recurrent infections, congestive heart failure, bone deformities, iron overload, splenomegaly, growth

retardation, jaundice, dark urine. Globally, it is the second most common hemoglobinopathy after sickle cell disease and it is common in malaria belt⁵. Pakistan is one of the leading countries that carry a significant burden of beta-thalassaemia. The general population of Pakistan has roughly 9.8 million carriers⁶. The commonly quoted figure for the country is 100,000 transfusions – dependent thalassaemia patients.

Healthy couples who are carriers of disease associated traits have a 25% chance of having major thalassaemic child with each pregnancy⁷. Long-term management of thalassaemia major patients involves life-long blood transfusion approximately after every 3-4 weeks, and management of iron overload complications. The main factor of thalassaemia prevalence with high frequency in Pakistan is consanguineous marriages. The mutated genes responsible for thalassaemia in Pakistan is not randomly distributed in the population but is restricted mostly to the affected families where intermarriages are common, leading to gene entrapment and proliferation⁸⁻¹⁰.

Hypothetically, *"In Pakistan, the high prevalence of thalassaemia is significantly influenced by consanguineous marriages, and ineffective prevention strategies, including comprehensive carrier screening and public awareness campaigns that can reduce the incidence of this genetic disorder"*⁹. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the epidemiological characteristics of thalassaemia patients in Khairpur, Sindh.

2. METHODOLOGY

This cross sectional descriptive study was conducted on Thalassaemia patients of Khairpur Mir's Sindh, Pakistan. The ethical approval for conducting this study was obtained from Institutional Ethical Review Board (IERB) Ref.No. 110 dated 21-03-2025. During research conduct the data of 97 patients was collected who were diagnosed with Thalassaemia. For analyzing the epidemiological characteristics of thalassaemia patients, the data was collected from the pathology laboratory of Fatimid foundation Khairpur city regarding the frequency, age, Hb level, gender and blood groups of thalassaemia patients. This research work was conducted within the period of three months from April 2025 to June 2025 at Fatimid Foundation pathology laboratory, located at Khairpur, Sindh. All the male and female patients of Thalassaemia were included in this study. The questionnaire was filled by observing their medical profile. Parents were informed about the aim of the study and data was collected. The collected data was statistically analyzed in Microsoft Excel 2010 and SPSS V 24.

3. RESULTS

This cross sectional descriptive study on the Prevalence of Thalassaemia patients was based on the survey that was conducted in the Fatimid Foundation Pathology Laboratory, Khairpur City, Sindh.

The Age wise frequency and Percentage of Thalassaemia patients were measured and results showed higher prevalence of Thalassaemia in age group 0-9 years with 73.2% (71 patients out of 97) than age group 10-17 years which was 22.7% (22 patients out of 97). The lowest percentage was seen in age group 18-25years which was 4.1% (4 patients out of 97) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Age wise frequency of thalassemia patients

AGE GROUPS	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
0-9 Year	71	73.2%
10-17Years	22	22.7%
18-25 Years	4	4.1%
Total	97	100%

The gender wise Percentage of male and female patients was calculated and it was observed greater in males than in female patients. Out of 97 patients included in this study, results exhibited

that 52 (53.6%) were males and 45 (46.4%) were females. The Table 2 shows frequency and percentage of males and females.

Table 2. Gender wise frequency of thalassemia patients

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Male	52	53.6
Female	45	46.4
Total	97	100.0

Thalassemia patient's data was categorized according to ABO blood groups. Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage of Thalassemia patients in different blood groups in which patients with "A" blood group were 30 (30.9%),

the patients having "B" blood group were 34 (35.1%), the patients having "AB" blood group were 8 (8.2%) and the patients having "O" blood group were 25 (25.8%).

Table 3. Blood group wise percentage of thalassemia patients

BLOOD GROUPS	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
A Blood Group	30	30.9%
B Blood group	34	35.1%
AB Blood Group	8	8.2%
O Blood Group	25	25.8%
Total	97	100.0%

The Hb level of subjects in three age groups was checked. Hb levels were divided in three categories (2.6-4g/dL, 5-7g/dL and 8-10g/dL). In age group 1 (0-9 years) 19 patients were diagnosed with low Hb level around 2.6-4g/dL, in age group

2 (10-17 years) 05 patients were diagnosed with low Hb level, and in age group 3 (18-25 years) 02 patients were diagnosed with low Hb level, shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Hb level and age groups

Normal Hb Level 10g/dL-15.5g/dL				
Age Groups	Hb LEVEL			Total
	2.6-4g/dL	5-7g/dL	8-10g/dL	
Group 1 (0-9 years)	19	15	37	71
Group 2 (10-17 years)	5	5	12	22
Group 3 (18-25 years)	2	0	2	4
				97

4. DISCUSSION

Thalassemia is inherited blood disorder characterized by mutated hemoglobin chain¹³. Thalassemia basically is of two types; depending upon defect in alpha or beta chain of hemoglobin. Among these two, beta Thalassemia is the most common genetic disorder¹⁴. Previous study reports that 3% of the world’s population carries the mutated genes for beta Thalassemia. It is estimated that carrier rate in Pakistan ranges between 5-8% per anum. Consanguinity is the major factor leading to high prevalence of thalassemia in Pakistan. Globally, it is the second most common hemoglobinopathy after sickle cell disease and it is common in malaria belt⁵. Pakistan is one of the leading countries that carry a significant burden of beta thalassaemia. The general population of Pakistan has roughly 9.8 million carriers⁶. The commonly quoted figure for the country is 100,000 transfusions - dependent thalassaemia patients. The present study that was conducted on 97 patients who had been diagnosed with Thalassemia, shows that majority of the patients were in early ages from birth to 9 years. This indicates that the frequency of thalassemia patients was high (71 patients) in this age group as shown in the study conducted by Areeba et al.,¹⁴, followed by 22 patients in the second age group (10 years to 17years) and 4 patients were in the third age group (17 years to 28 years). According to the finding of this study the ratio of male patients was higher than ratio of female patients. Gender wise distribution showed

higher frequency of male patients that was 52 patients and 45 female’s patients and similar data was shown in the study conducted by Siddiqui et al.,¹⁵. The age wise comparison showed that prevalence of thalassemia ratio higher in early aged children.

5. CONCLUSION

This cross-sectional study conducted in Khairpur, Sindh provides information regarding epidemiological characteristics of thalassemia patients. The results reveal that the thalassemia primarily affects children, with the highest cases in the 0-9 years age group, highlighting early onset and diagnosis. A slightly higher frequency of thalassemia was observed in males compared to females, which could be due to variations in healthcare access, or cultural factors. Highest frequency of thalassemia was noted in individuals having blood group B, while lowest frequency was observed in patients having AB blood group. Moreover, Hb level investigation across different age groups revealed the burden of anemia, spotlighting the chronic and transfusion dependent nature of thalassemia. These finding emphasizes the need for effective public health strategies, such as early screening of thalassemia, genetic counseling, and increased awareness. In future, research with larger sample size and molecular analysis is recommended to better understand the disease pattern.

6. REFERENCES

1. Khan WA. Thalassemia in Bangladesh. DS (Children) Hosp J 1999;15:42-4.
2. Ansari SH, Shamsi TS, Ashraf M, Bohray M, Farzana T, Khan MT, et al. Molecular epidemiology of Beta-thalassemia in Pakistan: Far reaching implication. Int J Mol Epidemiol Genet 2011; 2:403-8.
3. Shakeel M, Asif M, Rehman SU and Yaseen T (2016). Investigation of molecular heterogeneity of Beta-thalassemia disorder in district Charsadda Pakistan. Pak J. Med. Sci. 32:491-494.
4. Cazzola M, Borgna-Pignatti C, Locatelli F, Ponchio L, Beguin Y, De Stefano P. A moderate transfusion regimen may reduce iron loading in beta-thalassemia major without producing excessive expansion of erythropoiesis. Transfusion. 1997; 337:135-140.
5. Khalid N, Noreen K, Qureshi FM and Mahesar M (2019). Knowledge of thalassemia and consanguinity: A multi-center hospital based retrospective cohort study from metropolitan.
6. Ehsan H, Wahab A, Anwer F, Iftikhar R and Yousaf MN. (2020) n.d. Prevalence of Transfusion Transmissible Infections in Beta-Thalassemia Major Patients in Pakistan: A Systematic Review. Cureus 12. <http://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.10070>.
7. Yawn BP, Buchanan GR, Afeyi-Annan An, Ballas SK, Hassell KL, James AH, et al. Management of sickle cell disease summary of the 2014 Evidence-Based reported by expert panel Members. JAMA. 2014;312:1033-48.
8. Ahmed S. Thalassemia in Pakistan. J Islamic Intt Med Coll 2018; 13:50-1.
9. Verma IC, Choudhry VP, Jain PK. Prevention of thalassemia: A necessity in India J Pediatr 1992; 59:649-5.
10. Ahmed S, Saleem M, Sultana N, et al.: Prenatal diagnosis of beta-thalassemia in Pakistan: experience in a Muslim country. Prenat Diagn. 2000, 20:378-83. 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0223(200005)20:53.0.CO;2-7.
11. Safdar, S., Mirbahar, A., Sheikh, M. A., Taseer, I. U. H., Mustafa, A., Ali, Z., ... & Akhtar, T. (2017). Economic Burden of Thalassemia on Parents of Thalassemic Children: A Multi-Centre Study. Pakistan Journal of Medical Research, 56(3).
12. Zaman Q, Salahuddin M: Association between the education and thalassemia major: a statistical study. Pak J Stat Oper Res. 2006, 2103-10.
13. Ansari SH, Shamsi TS, Ahmed FN, Perveen K, Ahmed G. Effectiveness and feasibility of transabdominal chronic villous sampling procedure for prenatal diagnosis of β -thalassemia in a Muslim majority community of Pakistan. Pak J Med Sci 2012; 28(3): 575-9.
14. Areeba Aziz, Humna Tehreem, Rida Aslam, Waqar Alam Khan, Muhammad Umer Javed, Muhammad Sikander Ali, Aqsa Riaz, Muhammad Nouman Tariq, Syed Shayan Gilani, Seneen Noor, & Elyeen Noor. (2024). Consanguineous Marriages and Thalassemia Major in Pakistan: A Cross-Sectional Study On Awareness And Prevalence. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(07), 49-61.
15. Siddiqui, S. H., Ishtiaq, R., Sajid, F., Sajid, R. (2014). Quality of life in patients with thalassemia major in a developing country. *JCPSP: Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons-Pakistan*, 24(7), 477-480.